

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

INTEGRATED CARE IN ACUTE RESPIRATORY DISTRESS SYNDROME MANAGEMENT: COLLABORATIVE ROLES IN EMERGENCY, MEDICINE, NURSING, AND RADIOLOGY

Talal Maqbool Alamri^{1*}, Zain Jaber Alghamedi¹, Osama Faisal Alharbi², Malak Hussain Asiri³, Reem Naif Almutairi⁴, Hussain OBAID ALMUTAIRI⁴, Fatimah Hussain Asiri⁵, Nouf Saleem Hamdan Alsinani⁶, Hanan Matar Alharbi⁷, Ahmed Yaseen Alattas¹, Zainab Ali Abualsaud⁸, Najat Zakaria Ibrahim⁹, Faizah Atiahallah Alghamdi¹⁰, Waleed Khaled Tayeb¹¹, Rasha Khaled Sindy¹²

¹King Salman Medical City (KSMC)-Madinah, Mahzur, Madinah 42316, Saudi Arabia

²Heraa General Hospital, Makkah, Saudi Arabia.

³Riyadh Third Health Cluster, MQX6+M4V, Ar Rabwah, Riyadh 12821, Saudi Arabia

⁴Diabetic Center - Hafer Al Batin, CX7H+9C7, Al Baladiyah, Hafar Al Batin 39921, Saudi Arabia

⁵East Jeddah Hospital, First Cluster- Jeddah, 8742 King Abdallah Rd, Jeddah 22253, Saudi Arabia

⁶Aslam Marshood Rahaily Polyclinic, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

⁷Taif Health Cluster, Ministry Of Health, Al-Amana Street, Central District, Taif-26522, Saudi Arabia

⁸E1 Health Cluster, Minstrety Of Health, Dammam Medical Complex

⁹King Faisal Medical Complex-Taif, Shihar Road, Alhadaek, Taif 26514, Saudi Arabia

¹⁰King Abdullah Medical Complex-Jeddah, Prince Nayef Street, Northern Abhor, Jeddah 23816, Saudi Arabia

¹¹ Al-Noor Specialist Hospital-Makkah, 3rd Ring Rd, Al Hijrah, Makkah 24241, Saudi Arabia

¹²King Fahad General Hospital-Jeddah, Al Andalus· JCAB8231· 8231, Jeddah 23325, Saudi Arabia

Abstract:

Background: The condition known as acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) manifests through a quick buildup of pulmonary fluid, regardless of heart function, and extreme hypoxemia that fails to improve with typical therapies. Key characteristics involve bilateral lung opacities, decreased lung compliance, and pronounced inflammation resulting from capillary-alveolar membrane injury. ARDS can arise from direct lung insults, such as pneumonia or aspiration, or indirect factors like non-pulmonary sepsis, illustrating its diverse etiology. From a pathophysiological perspective, ARDS impairs gas exchange by compromising various lung regions, frequently resulting in pulmonary edema and exacerbated hypoxemia. Diagnosis necessitates the manifestation of symptoms within one week of a respiratory insult, identification of bilateral infiltrates via imaging, and ruling out cardiac complications. Supportive interventions, including low tidal volume ventilation and prone positioning, have been shown to enhance patient outcomes, yet mortality rates remain elevated (34–60%), often attributable to multiorgan failure. Predisposing factors encompass trauma, sepsis, and inhalation injuries, with severe manifestations associated with systemic inflammatory responses. The COVID-19 crisis has heightened the frequency of ARDS because of lung harm from pneumonia. Despite medical advancements, ARDS continues to impact approximately 150,000 individuals annually in the U.S., underscoring the need for persistent research aimed at improving treatment strategies and decreasing mortality. **Objective:** An overview of the Epidemiology, Prevalence, Stages, and Progression of (ARDS). **Methods:** A comprehensive review of acute respiratory distress syndrome. The PUBMED and Google Scholar search engines were the main databases used for the search process, with articles collected from 1997 to 2024. **Conclusion:** A comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach remains essential to managing this complex condition, with a focus on reducing mortality and addressing emerging challenges like the COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome, Classification, Collaboration, Laboratory, Management.

Corresponding author:**Talal Maqbool Alamri,**

King Salman Medical City (KSMC)-Madinah, Mahzur,

Madinah 42316, Saudi Arabia

E-mail: Talal066@yahoo.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Talal Maqbool Alamri et al., *Integrated Care In Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome Management: Collaborative Roles In Emergency, Medicine, Nursing, And Radiology.*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2024; 11 (12).

INTRODUCTION:

Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) is an exceptionally serious medical issue defined by the quick onset of lung fluid build-up that is not caused by heart issues, alongside a notable drop in respiratory ability, which frequently leads to worryingly elevated rates of illness and death in affected patients. This syndrome is delineated by several essential characteristics, which include extreme hypoxemia that does not respond positively to standard forms of respiratory support, diminished compliance of the thoracopulmonary system, as well as the observation of bilateral pulmonary opacities during imaging examinations such as X-rays or CT scans [Figure 1,2]. The underlying pathophysiological processes associated with ARDS encompass damage to the capillary-alveolar membranes, which subsequently leads to an elevation in pulmonary artery pressure and the consequential accumulation of inflammatory mediators within the alveolar spaces, thereby exacerbating the overall clinical picture and complicating management strategies (1). The condition we are examining could emerge from both direct harms to the lung system, which may show up as respiratory illnesses including pneumonia, and from indirect systemic inflammatory responses that are common in conditions not primarily targeting the lungs, as seen in nonpulmonary sepsis (2). Also, The heterogeneous and inhomogeneous characteristics inherent in lung injury associated with (ARDS) are of paramount significance when it comes to comprehensively grasping the profound implications it has on the physiological process of gas exchange; this phenomenon is often articulated in the literature as being organized into three distinct and clinically relevant zones, which are categorized as healthy (H), recruitable (R), and diseased (D).

In individuals suffering from ARDS, it is noteworthy that only the zones classified as healthy and recruitable actively participate in the critical process of gas exchange, a function that can be markedly hindered and disrupted as a direct consequence of the

pathological changes induced by the disease (1). Moreover, In the realm of diagnosing (ARDS), it is crucial to meet a specific set of well-defined criteria, prominently including the vital timing of symptom onset within a one-week window post a recognized and identifiable respiratory insult, alongside profound hypoxemia, and the necessary exclusion of any possible contributing factors like cardiac issues or fluid overload that may muddle the clinical understanding. This comprehensive and rigorous diagnostic framework is of paramount importance in facilitating the accurate differentiation of ARDS from a variety of other medical conditions, including but not limited to pneumonia and congestive heart failure, which may exhibit overlapping symptoms and clinical presentations; however, such conditions fundamentally possess unique and distinct underlying pathophysiological mechanisms that necessitate careful consideration in clinical practice.

Additionally, the care for (ARDS) mainly revolves around supportive tactics that are intentionally developed to maximize patient benefits, particularly emphasizing mechanical ventilation methods that can significantly lessen risks of lung injury; among these methods, utilizing low tidal volume ventilation and positioning patients in a prone manner has been reliably shown to improve clinical outcomes for individuals impacted by this syndrome. Furthermore, it is essential to appreciate that the offering of sufficient dietary support, paired with the careful administration of any underlying medical ailments the patient might be undergoing, is a significant aspect of comprehensive patient care in this framework. Regardless of the impressive advancements that have been accomplished in the area of supportive care techniques for ARDS, it is very disturbing to realize that the in-hospital mortality figures for individuals enduring severe symptoms of this syndrome continue to be excessively high, with reported rates oscillating between 46% and 60%, reinforcing the immediate necessity for persistent research and innovation in this sector (3).

Figure 1: Multifocal bilateral air-space opacities, in a predominantly perihilar and lower zone distribution (4).

Figure 2: The image on the right shows how ARDS increases lung inhomogeneities, especially in zones at the interface of regions with different aeration (voxels in red). *ARDS* acute respiratory distress syndrome, *CT* computed tomography, *HU* Hounsfield unit (5).

The epidemiological scenario regarding (ARDS) shows that this serious health issue influences a notably substantial number of nearly 150,000 people each year in the United States, with a distinct prevalence noted among those in intensive care units (ICUs) and individuals who need mechanical

ventilation support for breathing. Nonetheless, even with these alarming statistics, the authentic prevalence of ARDS continues to be obscured by a shroud of confusion, presenting a problem for both investigators and medical staff. Back in 1972, the NIH proposed that 150,000 new ARDS cases arise each year; yet, more updated analyses and reviews of existing studies show that the real occurrence of this condition might be

much less than previously thought, which calls for deeper inquiry into this variation. This notable divergence in reported incidence rates can be attributed to a myriad of challenges associated with the precise diagnosis of ARDS, the existence of variances in the definitions utilized across different studies, as well as the inherent difficulties involved in capturing comprehensive and representative data across the diverse populations affected by this serious medical condition (6).

Besides, the frequency of (ARDS) is considerably shaped by the magnitude and particularized traits of traumatic injuries that individuals face, reflecting a multifaceted relationship between the injury types and the following onset of this critical health situation. For example, empirical research has demonstrated that the incidence of ARDS emerged in approximately 0.5% of the studied patient population, though it is noteworthy that this rate escalated markedly among individuals who suffered from severe injuries or presented with multiple anatomical traumas, thereby underscoring the relationship between injury severity and ARDS prevalence. An alarming 83% of documented ARDS cases were found to correlate with high-energy trauma events, thereby emphasizing this mechanism as a pivotal risk factor contributing to the onset of the syndrome. Furthermore, the incidence of certain injury types, particularly femoral fractures and assorted combinations of injuries targeting both the abdominal area and the limbs, is recognized as a key predictor that could raise the likelihood of ARDS onset in impacted patients (7). In addition, the array of widely recognized risk elements contributing to the emergence of (ARDS) is extensive, reaching past mere traumatic occurrences, and includes an assortment of health issues like pneumonia, sepsis, and several kinds of inhalation injuries, each capable of causing both direct and indirect lung harm that significantly disrupts respiratory function. This specific physiological reaction starts and supports the gathering and later buildup of many kinds of inflammatory cells, like neutrophils, lymphocytes, and macrophages, within the lung tissue, a mechanism that greatly worsens the pre-existing damage and further endangers the integrity and functioning of the alveolar-capillary barrier, which is vital for ensuring proper respiratory activities and gas exchange (8). In context, The detailed biological processes behind (ARDS) reveal a complex and shifting interaction of diverse inflammatory activities along with important structural modifications in the lung area. When ARDS first develops, the alveolar-capillary barrier becomes notably compromised, which then causes an escalation in permeability, culminating in the pathological retention of fluid laden with proteins inside the alveoli;

this condition is clinically termed pulmonary edema. The presence of this excess fluid within the alveoli severely disrupts the essential processes of normal gas exchange, thereby significantly contributing to the development of pronounced hypoxemia, a condition that frequently exhibits resistance to standard forms of oxygen therapy typically employed in clinical practice (1, 8).

In addition, the identification of bilateral infiltrates observed on a chest X-ray serves as a definitive hallmark diagnostic characteristic, which intricately signifies the underlying processes of fluid accumulation and the consequential inflammatory alterations occurring within the pulmonary structures of the lungs. Besides, An advantageous outcome in the instance of (ARDS) is recognized by a significant decline in the quantities of several inflammatory mediators that impact the pathophysiological transitions, in tandem with the critical movement of fibroblasts into the affected tissues, the later layering of collagen to restore structural stability, and the successful reabsorption of surplus fluid from edema that has accumulated in the lung interstitial (8). Also, understanding that the recovery timeline after experiencing (ARDS) can often be protracted is important, as this length is significantly determined by both the level of severity related to the original lung injury sustained and the various contributing factors that lead to the occurrence of ARDS initially. The elaborate and diverse aspects of the linked pathophysiological dynamics that typify ARDS not only point out the substantial obstacles experienced in the pursuit of formulating and applying efficient therapeutic measures but also stress the importance of a detailed grasp of these complicated interrelations to better clinical outcomes for impacted individuals. Nevertheless, The mortality rates that are associated with the occurrence of ARDS are strikingly and alarmingly elevated, exhibiting a range that fluctuates between 34% and 55%, with the majority of fatalities that arise in connection with this syndrome being primarily attributed to the subsequent onset of multiorgan failure that follows an initial episode of respiratory failure (9).

Apprehending the elaborate and intricate factors contributing to (ARDS) is vital for executing effective treatment protocols and management tactics focused on this critical ailment. The primary underlying causes of ARDS can be systematically categorized into two distinct but interrelated categories, namely direct and indirect insults that adversely affect the pulmonary system [Figure 3]. Direct pulmonary insults encompass a range of pathological conditions, including but not limited to pneumonia and aspiration

events, both of which have been extensively studied in the context of ARDS. The infectious disease known as pneumonia causes inflammation in the lung's air sacs, or alveoli, and can lead to considerable lung impairment, being a recognized contributor to ARDS. Similarly, aspiration, which denotes the unintentional drawing in of external materials, including food bits or liquids, into the lungs, can initiate a significant inflammatory reaction that greatly aids in the harmful progression of ARDS (10). On the other hand, it is essential to recognize that indirect insults to the body often arise from a variety of systemic inflammatory conditions, with sepsis serving as a particularly notable and prominent example within this category of illnesses.

When the body responds improperly to an infection, a serious state called sepsis can occur, which may lead to the onset of ARDS due to organ dysfunction. Notably, nonpulmonary sepsis is specifically acknowledged within the medical literature as an indirect causative factor that contributes to the onset of ARDS, thereby underscoring the intricate and

multifaceted interplay that exists between systemic infections and resultant lung injury (2). Additionally, Several noteworthy and essential etiological components that are linked to this condition consist of thromboembolism taking place in the pulmonary arteries, a clinical occurrence that might obstruct the standard blood circulation through these vital vessels, eventually causing the serious and potentially fatal issue of acute respiratory failure (10). Yet, the current scenario in global health reveals that the unparalleled spread of the COVID-19 pandemic has underscored the necessity of comprehending the origins of (ARDS), particularly as serious pneumonia and marked lung inflammation linked to the infection have triggered a substantial uptick in ARDS occurrences within affected groups. This instance not only illustrates the essential requirement for continuous and rigorous research activities intended to clarify the multifarious causes of ARDS but also underscores the vital need to improve patient outcomes by innovating more targeted and efficient treatment options that engage the specific mechanisms underlying this complex syndrome.

Figure 3: Causes of acute respiratory distress syndrome (11).

Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome initial assessment

The determination of (ARDS) is predominantly reliant upon an intricate amalgamation of various clinical indicators alongside a set of specific

diagnostic benchmarks that are recognized in the medical community. Among the most critical indicators that signify the presence of this condition are severe episodes of dyspnea, pronounced tachypnea, and notable cyanosis, all of which serve as manifestations that indicate considerable respiratory

distress and the resultant hypoxemia that the patient is experiencing (12). Also, The Berlin Definition of (ARDS), officially set in the year 2012, serves as a thorough guideline for identifying the various levels of severity connected to this complex syndrome, mainly determined by the ratio of arterial oxygen partial pressure (PaO₂) to the fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO₂), with a critical threshold value of ≤ 200 indicating severe ARDS manifestations, highlighting a significant drop in respiratory capability. Also, this broadly recognized definition points out the essential requirement for instituting a minimum positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) of 5 cm H₂O, a criterion viewed as indispensable for maintaining proper oxygenation levels in the patient's respiratory framework, thereby aiding in improved clinical results and overall syndrome treatment (13). Furthermore, the comprehensive assessment of total thoracic compliance is conducted to meticulously evaluate lung function, which subsequently facilitates a deeper understanding of the extent and severity of the pathological respiratory condition encountered in the patient (14).

Nevertheless, the initial evaluation and assessment of the patient in question must also take into account the critical consideration of the absence of left atrial hypertension, a factor that holds significant importance in the confirmation of a diagnosis of (ARDS). This extensive and varied tactic not only assures that doctors are capable of correctly spotting the manifestation of ARDS but also permits them to effectively tell it apart from several other respiratory issues that may display alike clinical signs and symptoms. Despite the substantial improvements in our understanding of ARDS's pathophysiology and diagnostic benchmarks, it remains important to recognize that treatment methods primarily continue to be supportive, especially focusing on mechanical ventilation tactics crafted to lessen the chances of further lung injury. The rising consciousness about the possible negative effects caused by mechanical ventilation methods has thus encouraged the innovation and refinement of protective ventilation protocols, designed to significantly cut down the frequency of lung injury induced by ventilators in those affected (15).

Current Management Strategies for ARDS

Current management strategies, which are employed in the context of respiratory distress syndromes, are primarily concentrated on the critical objectives of optimizing ventilation dynamics, minimizing the incidence of lung injury, and providing comprehensive supportive care measures to enhance patient outcomes. A pivotal and foundational technique that has gained

traction in the care of (ARDS) is the adoption of prone positioning, an approach that has been empirically verified to substantially improve oxygen levels and enhance lung mechanics when facing severe illness. This technique proves to be especially advantageous for patients who are suffering from refractory hypoxemia, as it facilitates the recruitment of collapsed areas of the lung and concurrently reduces the phenomenon of shunting, which can exacerbate hypoxic conditions. When considering prone positioning, it is equally vital to implement substantial positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) in this clinical situation. The utilization of elevated PEEP levels plays a critical role in maintaining lung recruitment and preventing collapse during the process of mechanical ventilation, which in turn contributes to the overall improvement of oxygenation across the respiratory system (16). Also, Ventilation strategies have undergone remarkable advancements over time, with a pronounced focus on the imperative need for lung protection in clinical settings. This modern approach encompasses the adoption of low tidal volume ventilation techniques, which specifically utilize significantly lower tidal volumes ranging from 4 to 6 mL per kilogram of body weight, in stark contrast to the more traditional methodologies that typically employ tidal volumes between 10 and 12 mL per kilogram. The rationale behind this innovative strategy is to effectively minimize the potential for ventilator-induced lung injury, which is primarily achieved by substantially reducing the likelihood of volutrauma, a detrimental condition that arises from the application of excessively high tidal volumes during mechanical ventilation. Furthermore, the lung protection paradigm frequently integrates the use of elevated positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) to avert the occurrence of atelectrauma, a pathological phenomenon characterized by the collapse of lung tissue that can compromise respiratory function and overall pulmonary health (17).

Moreover, Permissive hypercapnia is a pertinent and significant management strategy that facilitates the allowance of elevated concentrations of carbon dioxide within the bloodstream, thereby contributing to the reduction of ventilator-induced lung injury, which is a common complication associated with mechanical ventilation. This approach proves to be exceptionally beneficial in achieving a delicate equilibrium between the necessity for sufficient ventilation to maintain adequate gas exchange and the imperative to minimize potential damage to the lung parenchyma and overall respiratory system. Furthermore, the implementation of open lung ventilation techniques is specifically designed with the primary objective of sustaining optimal lung

recruitment while simultaneously minimizing the incidence of lung collapse, thereby providing significant support for the comprehensive management and therapeutic intervention strategies employed in addressing (ARDS). Also, In remarkably urgent cases of (ARDS), it is commonly critical to engage in advanced healthcare techniques, one of which is recognized as Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation (ECMO), a refined system that boosts oxygen availability and supports the extraction of carbon dioxide from the blood. ECMO serves a vital role in providing respiratory support, especially in situations where traditional mechanical ventilation strategies fail to meet the physiological demands of the patient, thereby representing a crucial and life-saving salvage therapy option for individuals suffering from profound respiratory failure. Additional salvage therapy modalities that may be employed in such critical cases include high-frequency ventilation and inverse-ratio ventilation, both of which fundamentally modify the ratio of inspiratory to expiratory time, thereby optimizing the process of oxygenation and potentially improving overall respiratory function in affected patients (16).

Importance of Integrated Care in ARDS Management

When dealing with (ARDS), the role of integrated care is vital, promoting collaboration among different healthcare specialists and making sure that patients are offered a complete and systematically arranged strategy for their medical attention, thus meeting the varied aspects of their health demands. Integrated Care Pathways (ICPs) assume a critical function in this intricate process by significantly enhancing the flow of communication among various healthcare disciplines, which is indispensable for the proficient management of complex medical conditions such as ARDS that require a multidisciplinary approach. Implementing Integrated Care Pathways is essential for enhancing interprofessional dialogue, breaking down the barriers within healthcare, and also encouraging richer interactions between patients and their caregivers, which directly influences patient satisfaction and optimal clinical outcomes (18). Besides, A core factor that is pivotal to the proficient administration of (ARDS) resides in the execution of a holistic method, which not only highlights the necessity of conducting daily examinations of patient data by every member of the healthcare team but also underscores the collective obligation of each practitioner engaged. This diligent practice facilitates a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the patient's evolving condition, thereby ensuring that all healthcare professionals are not only aware of but also

synchronized in their treatment strategies, which is essential for optimizing patient outcomes. Furthermore, engaging in thorough discussions concerning patient-specific problems among the various team members is of paramount importance, as such interactions significantly contribute to a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the intricate complexities that are inherently involved in the multifaceted management of ARDS. The combination of these discussions, along with the clear and effective communication of the therapy plan, culminates in a well-organized and efficacious treatment regimen, which is critical considering the highly intricate and multifaceted nature of this debilitating illness (19).

CONCLUSION:

Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) is a life-threatening condition marked by rapid lung fluid accumulation, severe hypoxemia, and reduced lung compliance. Its pathophysiology involves alveolar-capillary barrier damage, inflammation, and pulmonary edema, often triggered by pneumonia, aspiration, sepsis, or systemic inflammation. Despite advancements in understanding and diagnostics, ARDS remains a significant challenge, with high mortality rates, often due to multiorgan failure. Management focuses on supportive care, including mechanical ventilation strategies like low tidal volume, prone positioning, and elevated positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) to improve oxygenation and reduce ventilator-induced lung injury. Advanced therapies, such as Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation (ECMO), offer critical support in severe cases. Collaborative care through Integrated Care Pathways (ICPs) is vital for addressing the complex needs of ARDS patients, fostering interprofessional communication and synchronized treatment strategies. Ongoing research and refinement of therapeutic approaches, including protective ventilation, permissive hypercapnia, and open lung techniques, aim to improve outcomes. A comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach remains essential to managing this complex condition, with a focus on reducing mortality and addressing emerging challenges like the COVID-19 pandemic.

Author Contributions

The original text was written by the corresponding author, however all writers made substantial contributions by gathering data and doing a literature search for article. Each author approved the final draft of the manuscript, took responsibility for all aspects of it, and took part in its critical revision of manuscript.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge and deeply appreciate the contributions of authors, open access data bases, web portal and publishers whose works provided the essential literature for the completion of this article.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare they don't have any conflict of interest.

Ethical Approval

Not Applicable

REFERENCES:

- Lewandowski K, Rossaint R, Falke KJ. Step-by-Step Treatment of Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome. In: Reinhart K, Eyrich K, Sprung C, editors. Sepsis: Current Perspectives in Pathophysiology and Therapy. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg; 1994. p. 539-48.
- Nadon AS, Schmidt EP. Pathobiology of the Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome. In: McManus LM, Mitchell RN, editors. Pathobiology of Human Disease. San Diego: Academic Press; 2014. p. 2665-76.
- Chiumello D, Marino A, Cammaroto A. The Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome: Diagnosis and Management. In: Chiumello D, editor. Practical Trends in Anesthesia and Intensive Care 2018. Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2019. p. 189-204.
- Matthay MA, Zemans RL, Zimmerman GA, Arabi YM, Beitler JR, Mercat A, et al. Acute respiratory distress syndrome. Nature reviews Disease primers. 2019;5(1):18.
- Bitker L, Talmor D, Richard JC. Imaging the acute respiratory distress syndrome: past, present and future. Intensive Care Med. 2022;48(8):995-1008.
- Hudson LD, Steinberg KP, editors. Epidemiology of ARDS. Incidence and Outcome: A Changing Picture 1998; Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- White TO, Jenkins PJ, Smith RD, Carlidge CWJ, Robinson CM. The Epidemiology of Posttraumatic Adult Respiratory Distress Syndrome. 2004;86(11):2366-76.
- Chiumello D, Valente Barbas CS, Pelosi P. Pathophysiology of ARDS. In: Lucangelo U, Pelosi P, Zin WA, Aliverti A, editors. Respiratory System and Artificial Ventilation. Milano: Springer Milan; 2008. p. 101-17.
- Zhu Y-f, Feng X, Lu X-L, Ying W, Chen J-L, Chao J-x, et al. Mortality and morbidity of acute hypoxemic respiratory failure and acute respiratory distress syndrome in infants and young children. 2012;125(13):2265-71.
- Ziliene V, Kondrotas AJ, Kevelaitis EJM. Etiology and pathogenesis of acute respiratory failure. 2004;40(3):286-94.
- Bos LDJ, Ware LB. Acute respiratory distress syndrome: causes, pathophysiology, and phenotypes. The Lancet. 2022;400(10358):1145-56.
- Obertacke U, Joka T, Neumann C. Development of a Linear Scoring System. In: Sturm JA, editor. Adult Respiratory Distress Syndrome: An Aspect of Multiple Organ Failure Results of a Prospective Clinical Study. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg; 1991. p. 25-9.
- Patry C, Orfanos SE, Rafat N. Translational research in ARDS patients: new biological phenotypes. Intensive Care Medicine. 2015;41(11):1986-9.
- Macnaughton PD, Hunter DN, Evans TW, editors. Physiological Assessment of Acute Lung Injury in the Intensive Care Unit 1992; Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Mahto HL, Shenoy A, Unnikrishnan RJIJoRC. Initial oxygenation as an early predictor of mortality in acute respiratory distress syndrome: a retrospective study. 2015;4(1):554.
- O'Connor MF, Hall JB. ARDS: Current Treatment and Ventilator Strategies. Anesthesiology Clinics of North America. 1998;16(1):155-80.
- Jabbari A, Alijanpour E, Maleh PA, Heidari BJCJoIM. Lung protection strategy as an effective treatment in acute respiratory distress syndrome. 2013;4(1):560.
- Hotchkiss RJNR. Integrated care pathways. 1997;2(1):30-6.
- Clemmer TP, Orme JF. AN INTEGRATED APPROACH TO THE PATIENT WITH ACUTE RESPIRATORY FAILURE. Clinics in Chest Medicine. 1982;3(1):171-9.